

Synthesis of amino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinones

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Three isomers of amino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone **5** were prepared by reductions of the corresponding nitro compounds **4**, which were prepared by nitration of 1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone **3** with $\text{HNO}_3/(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2\text{O}$ at 0° .

Ever since the synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone **3**¹, there has been growing interest in the synthesis of its derivatives and evaluation of their biological activities^{2,3}. A variety of the derivatives of compound **1** were synthesized in our laboratory^{4,5}. Compared to ibuprofen, some of them showed similar anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities and lower side-effects. Among them, the amino derivatives are more promising compounds.

Scheme 1

Compound **3** can be synthesized by two methods from 3-(1-pyrrolyl)propionitrile **2**^{4,6}, and the method of $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-NaCl-KCl}$ system was employed in the present study (Scheme 1). The aminopyrrolizinones **5** were prepared by catalytic hydrogenation of the corresponding nitropyrrolizinones, which were prepared by nitration of **3**. Based on the nitration of pyrrole, the reaction was carried out with a solution of HNO_3 in $(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2\text{O}$. After work up, a brown-red oil was obtained. The TLC showed that it was a mixture containing three major components. Chromato-

graphed with silica gel column, three products **4a**, **4b** and **4c** were obtained in a ratio of about 3 : 1 : 1. Both the nitro- and aminopyrrolizinones were not found in literature. The three products of the nitration showed molecular ion peaks at m/z 166 in MS and IR absorptions of nitro group at around 1500 (ν_{as}) and 1350 cm^{-1} (ν_{s}). ^1H NMR spectrum showed the nitration to occur at the pyrrole ring moiety (the 5, 6 and 7 position), and the three compounds to be isomers. They have similar chemical shifts for the aliphatic hydrogens at around δ 3.1 and 4.4, but for the aromatic hydrogens, the chemical shifts and the splittings are apparently different. Compound **4b**, red needle crystals, m.p. $184\text{--}186^\circ$, has two singlets at δ 8.35 and 7.23, each singlet corresponding to one hydrogen. The singlets mean that there are no couplings between the two hydrogens. Therefore, this compound should be assigned as 6-nitro derivative of compound **3**. Both compound **4a** (colorless crystals, m.p. $115\text{--}117^\circ$) and **4c** (yellow crystals, m.p. $153\text{--}155^\circ$) have two doublets at δ 6.77, 7.38 and 7.42, 7.12, respectively. Besides the difference of the chemical shifts, the splittings of the doublets are apparently different. The coupling constant of the doublet of **4a** is 4.5 Hz, while that of **4c** is 2.7 Hz. Compared with the coupling constants of pyrrole ($J_{\beta-\beta}$ 3–4, $J_{\alpha-\beta}$ 2–3 Hz) and compound **1** (J_{6-7} 3.84 and J_{5-6} 2.23 Hz), it can be found that $J_{\beta-\beta}$ of the pyrrole (corresponding to the J_{6-7} of compound **3**) is obviously higher than $J_{\alpha-\beta}$ (corresponding to the J_{5-6} of compound **3**). Apparently, compound **4a** shows higher coupling constant (4.5 Hz) than **4c** (2.7 Hz). Therefore, **4a** was designed as 5-nitro-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone, and **4c** as 7-nitro-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone.

Several types of derivatives of 5-aminopyrrolizinone were prepared with the reactions occurring at the amino

group. Some of the derivatives showed significant analgesic or/and anti-inflammatory activities on acetic-induced writhing and xylene-induced ear edema of mouse, for example, compounds YZ-245 and YZ-251 (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1. Effects of compounds on xylene-induced mouse ear edema^a

Compd.	Swelling mg, $\bar{X} \pm SD$	Inhibition rate %
Saline	15.99 $\pm$ 4.68	–
Ibuprofen	10.41 $\pm$ 3.20 ^a	34.9
YZ-245	6.30 $\pm$ 2.09 ^b	60.6
YZ-251	10.72 $\pm$ 5.42 ^c	33.0

^aCompound with control; ^bP, <0.01; ^cP, <0.001, ^dP <0.05.

Table 2. Effects of compounds on acetic acid-induced mouse writhing^a

Compd.	Writhing $\bar{X} \pm SD$	Inhibition rate %
Saline	46.00 $\pm$ 20.74	–
Ibuprofen	9.40 $\pm$ 7.43 ^a	79.6
YZ-245	19.11 $\pm$ 9.70	58.5
YZ-251	12.56 $\pm$ 10.39 ^b	72.7

^aExplanation same as in Table 1.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined using a Yanaco melting point microscope and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Bruker IR-FIS-55 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker ARX-300 (300 MHz) instrument using TMS as an internal standard in DMSO-*d*₆ except **5a** and **5c** in CDCl₃ and mass spectra on a Shimadzu GCMS-QP5050A spectrometer. The elemental analyses were carried out using a Carlo Erba-1106 analyzer.

3-(1-Pyrrolyl)propionitrile (2): A solution of **1** (31.5 ml, 0.455 mol) and 40% aq. benzyltriethylammonium hydroxide (TB; 3.8 ml) was cooled to 5°. It was slowly added to acrylonitrile (47.0 ml, 0.72 mol) at 8–12°. The solution was then stirred at the same condition for 30 min and at the room temperature for 1 h. By distillation under reduced pressure and collecting 132–135°/14 mm distillation cut, a colorless liquid (48.6 g, 89%) was obtained.

1,2-Dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (3): A mixture of finely ground aluminum chloride (56 g, 0.421 mol), NaCl (11.6 g, 0.197 mol) and KCl (11.6 g, 0.157 mol) was heated to form a clear brown melt. When temperature dropped to 120°, 3-(1-pyrrolyl)propionitrile (15 g, 0.125 mol) was rapidly added, and the mixture after vigorous stirring for 2 min,

was poured quickly into stirred ice-water (800 g). The mixture was stirred at 35–40° and 85–90° for 1 h, respectively. It was then cooled to room temperature, extracted with dichloromethane and dried over sodium sulfate. The solvent was removed and the residue crystallized from ether-light petroleum to give the product (7.5 g, 75%), m.p. 53–55°, δ 3.10 (2H, t, *J* 6.20 Hz, 2-CH₂), 4.32 (2H, t, *J* 6.20 Hz, 3-CH₂), 6.53 (1H, dd, *J* 2.24, 3.94 Hz, 6-H), 6.74 (1H, dd, *J* 0.94 Hz, 7-H), 7.05 (1H, s, 5-H).

Nitro-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (4a-c): A solution of **3** (1.21 g, 10 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was added slowly to 67% HNO₃ (0.68 ml, 0.015 mol) at 0°. After stirring for 2 h at 20°, the mixture was poured into water (30 ml) and further stirred for 30 min, and finally extracted with dichloromethane. The organic layer was washed with water and dried over sodium sulfate. The solvent was removed and the residue separated by silica gel column chromatography (ethyl acetate-petroleum, 1 : 4) to yield three products **4a**, **4b** and **4c** in ratio of about 3 : 1 : 1.

5-Nitro-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (4a): It was obtained in 48% yield, m.p. 115–117° (Found: C, 50.59; H, 3.58; N, 16.90. Calcd. for C₇H₆N₂O₃ (166.04): C, 50.63; H, 3.61; N, 16.86%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1708 (C=O), 1512 (NO₂), 1369 cm⁻¹ (NO₂); ¹H NMR δ 3.10 (2H, t, *J* 5.65 Hz, 2-CH₂), 4.64 (2H, t, *J* 5.65 Hz, 3-CH₂), 6.77 (1H, d, *J* 4.47 Hz, 6-H), 7.38 (1H, d, *J* 4.47 Hz, 7-H); ¹³C NMR δ 38.4 (CH₂), 45.4 (CH₂), 105.9 (CH), 116.2 (CH), 135.5 (C_q), 135.7 (C_q), 191.2 (C=O); *m/z* 166 (M⁺, base peak).

6-Nitro-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (4b): It was obtained in 17% yield, m.p. 184–186° (Found: C, 50.57; H, 3.59; N, 16.89. Calcd. for C₇H₆N₂O₃ (166.04): C, 50.63; H, 3.61; N, 16.86%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1712 (C=O), 1502 cm⁻¹ (NO₂); ¹H NMR δ 3.02 (2H, t, *J* 6.25 Hz, 2-CH₂), 4.40 (2H, t, *J* 6.25 Hz, 3-CH₂), 7.23 (1H, s, 7-H), 8.35 (1H, s, 5-H); ¹³C NMR δ 38.4 (CH₂), 43.7 (CH₂), 101.3 (CH), 123.0 (CH), 130.9 (C_q), 140.5 (C_q), 191.8 (C=O); *m/z* 166 (M⁺, base peak).

7-Nitro-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (4c): It was obtained in a yield of 16%, m.p. 153–155° (Found: C, 50.56; H, 3.60; N, 16.92. Calcd. for C₇H₆N₂O₃ (166.04): C, 50.63; H, 3.61; N, 16.86%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1712 (C=O), 1497 (NO₂), 1358 cm⁻¹ (NO₂); ¹H NMR δ 3.10 (2H, t, *J* 5.85 Hz, 2-CH₂), 4.36 (2H, t, *J* 5.85 Hz, 3-CH₂), 7.12 (1H, d, *J* 2.75 Hz, 6-H), 7.42 (1H, d, *J* 2.75 Hz, 5-H); ¹³C NMR δ 37.9 (CH₂), 42.5 (CH₂), 111.9 (CH), 122.0 (CH), 126.8 (C_q), 129.9 (C_q), 186.2 (C=O); *m/z* 166 (M⁺, base peak).

Amino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinones (5a-c). **General procedure**: To nitro-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinones (**4a-c**; 1.36 g, 0.010 mol) dissolved in methanol (50 ml) was added

10% Pd/C (0.15 g) and hydrogenated by H₂ at 20–25° and 1 atm pressure till the reaction solution did not absorb the hydrogen gas. The solution was then filtered and concentrated. The pure materials were obtained by crystallization from ethyl acetate and light petroleum.

5-Amino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (5a) : It was obtained in yield of 98%, m.p. 177–178° (Found : C, 61.74; H, 5.86; N, 20.63. Calcd. for C₇H₈N₂O (136.06) : C, 61.79; H, 5.88; N, 20.58%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3352 (NH₂), 3195 (NH₂), 1608 cm⁻¹ (C=O); ¹H NMR δ 3.06 (2H, t, *J* 6.22 Hz, 2-CH₂), 3.76 (2H, s, NH₂), 4.03 (2H, t, *J* 6.22 Hz, 3-CH₂), 5.78 (1H, d, *J* 4.01 Hz, 6-H), 6.70 (1H, d, *J* 4.01 Hz, 7-H); *m/z* 136 (M⁺, 80 (base peak, M-[C₃H₄O]⁺).

6-Amino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (5b) : It was obtained in 70% yield, m.p. 114–117° (Found : C, 61.75; H, 5.85; N, 20.65. Calcd. for C₇H₈N₂O (136.06); C, 61.79; H, 5.88; N, 20.58%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3432 (NH₂), 3333 (NH₂), 1653 cm⁻¹ (C=O); ¹H NMR δ 2.82 (2H, t, *J* 5.80 Hz, 2-CH₂), 4.12 (2H, t, *J* 5.80 Hz, 3-CH₂), 4.39 (2H, s, NH₂), 5.86 (1H, d, *J* 0.81 Hz, 7-H), 6.70 (1H, d, *J* 0.81 Hz, 5-H); *m/z* 136 (M⁺, base peak).

7-Amino-1,2-dihydro-1-pyrrolizinone (5c) : It was obtained in 97% yield, m.p. 164–165° (Found : C, 61.73; H, 5.83; N, 20.66. Calcd. for C₇H₈N₂O (136.06) : C, 61.79; H, 5.88; N, 20.58%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3448 (NH₂), 3318 (NH₂), 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=O); ¹H NMR δ 2.81 (2H, t, *J* 6.36 Hz, 2-CH₂), 4.05 (2H, t, *J* 6.36 Hz, 3-CH₂), 4.92 (2H, s, NH₂), 5.62 (1H, d, *J* 2.18 Hz, 6-H), 6.91 (1H, d, *J* 2.18, Hz, 5-H); *m/z* 136 (M⁺, base peak).

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